

Reaction of But-1-ene with Hydrogen over Molybdenum Disulphide Catalyst

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The reaction of but-1-ene with hydrogen has been studied over 'fresh' and hydrogen sulphide 'treated' molybdenum disulphide catalysts. The course of reaction, kinetics and activation energies for hydrogenation and isomerisation have been determined along with the variation in product distributions with hydrogen uptake, initial reactant pressure and temperature. But-1-ene isomerisation also occurs in the absence of molecular hydrogen. Treatment of the catalyst with hydrogen sulphide retarded the hydrogenation activity of the catalyst. Two kinds of active sites with different degree of coordinative unsaturation have been proposed; isomerisation and hydrogenation occur on different sites.

THERE are a few reports on sorption of hydrogen^{1,2}, hydroisomerisation and/or hydrogen exchange of olefin on sulphide catalysts³⁻⁵. The hydrogen sulphide treated MoS₂ showed much diminished activity for hydrogenation reaction of ethylene⁴. In the present studies, the catalytic properties of freshly prepared MoS₂ and hydrogen sulphide treated MoS₂ have been investigated for hydrogenation and isomerisation of but-1-ene.

Experimental

The preparation of molybdenum disulphide catalyst, purification of chemicals and the general procedure adopted for the present studies were similar to those described elsewhere⁶. The conventional high vacuum apparatus incorporated a reaction vessel, a mercury manometer, storage vessels for reactants, liquid nitrogen trap to separate the reaction products from the unreacted hydrogen and gas chromatography⁷ system for analysis. The catalyst (surface area, 4.3 m² g⁻¹), usually 500 mg, was distributed over the bottom of the reaction vessel. The catalyst was evacuated for 30 min at room temperature, then the temperature was raised to 350°, with the catalyst maintained under vacuum. Reactions were carried out by admitting a suitable pressure (150 torr) of reaction mixture with hydrogen/but-1-ene ratio of 2:1. The products were analysed at a pressure-fall corresponding to the desired extent of reaction.

Results

Fig. 1 shows a typical pressure-fall against time curve for the reaction of but-1-ene with hydrogen. It can be seen from the first order plot that the

Fig. 1. A typical pressure fall against time curve for the reaction of but-1-ene with hydrogen (hydrogen pressure = 100 torr and but-1-ene-pressure = 50 torr), also shown is the plot to test for first order.

overall order of reaction is not one. The hydrogenation reactions were carried out over fresh sample of catalyst and the products were analysed after varying pressure-falls. It can be observed (Fig. 2) that butene distribution attained thermodynamic equilibrium proportions⁸ at fairly low conversion to n-butene. An attempt was made to perturb the *trans/cis* equilibrium ratio at certain stage (pressure-fall 25 torr) of reaction by admitting an additional amount (25 torr) of but-1-ene to the reaction mixture. The butene percentage composition varied at first, but the *trans/cis* ratio remained almost unaltered. As the reaction proceeded the butenes tended towards their thermodynamic equilibrium composition. The effect of hydrogen sulphide towards the hydrogenation and isomerisation activity of the catalyst was studied by treating

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Fig. 2. The variation of butene distribution with increasing extent of reaction over fresh MoS_2 at 350° .

it with an excess amount ($22.9 \mu\text{m}$) of hydrogen sulphide at 350° for a period of 2 h and the catalyst was then evacuated at the same temperature for 30 min. The hydrogen sulphide treated catalyst exhibited much lower hydrogenation activity, whereas isomerisation activity was hardly affected. The but-1-ene isomerisation in the absence of molecular hydrogen was tested at 350° using but-1-ene pressure of 25 torr. The products were analysed after varying periods of time (Fig. 3). The isomerisation of but-1-ene to its corresponding isomers was much slower than in the presence of hydrogen as may be anticipated.

Fig. 3. The isomerisation of but-1-ene over a fresh MoS_2 catalyst at 350° .

The initial rate orders with respect to hydrogen and but-1-ene were evaluated over a pressure range 25–350 torr at 350° using fresh catalyst. Initial rates of hydrogenation were determined from pressure-fall against time curves. The orders of reaction were 0.5 ± 0.1 and 0.65 ± 0.1 , respectively, for hydrogen and but-1-ene.

The effect of temperature in the range $290 - 414^\circ$ was studied using a but-1-ene/hydrogen ratio 1 : 2 (150 torr). The reaction products were analysed

at a fixed pressure-fall of 5 torr. For fresh and hydrogen sulphide treated catalyst, values of activation energy were respectively, 11.0 ± 2.0 and $12.0 \pm 1.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The activation energy of isomerisation of but-1-ene in the absence of molecular hydrogen was calculated in the temperature range $300 - 415^\circ$ using but-1-ene pressure of 25 torr, which was found to be 17.0 kJ mol^{-1} .

Discussion

Two possible reaction schemes may be considered in attempting to elucidate the mechanism whereby isomerisation of but-1-ene occurs: (i) an addition-elimination mechanism, involving the formation of 2-butyl intermediates, and (ii) an elimination-addition mechanism, involving the formation of 1-methyl- π -allyl intermediate. In mechanism (i), the presence of hydrogen is essential, whereas in mechanism (ii), its presence is not required. In postulating different mechanisms for hydrogenation and isomerisation, it can be proposed that these reactions take place independently on different sites. Under all conditions, isomerisation was found to be more favourable reaction compared with hydrogenation. The results obtained from the isomerisation of but-1-ene in the absence of molecular hydrogen suggest to consider an elimination-addition mechanism, whereas the presence of molecular hydrogen is necessary for an alkyl reversal mechanism to be operative. It is found that hydrogen markedly enhances isomerisation and butene distribution attains thermodynamic equilibrium composition at an early stage of hydrogenation reaction.

The retarding effect of hydrogen sulphide towards the hydrogenation activity of MoS_2 is significant, while the isomerisation of but-1-ene to but-2-ene (double bond migration) is not effected at all. This makes to postulate two types of active sites on the surface: one responsible for isomerisation, while the other active for hydrogenation. Treatment of the catalyst with hydrogen sulphide produces HS group on the surface, thus reducing the coordinative unsaturation with respect to sulphur of the molybdenum by introducing another sulphur atom. Since olefin hydrogenation occurs on C-sites²⁻⁵, therefore, hydrogen sulphide would act as catalyst poison by conversion of these sites to B or A. This has been obtained in case of ethylene hydrogenation on MoS_2 at ambient temperature, the ethylene hydrogenation was negligible after the catalyst treated with hydrogen sulphide⁴. Similar information has been obtained in our earlier studies on the hydrogenation of *cis*-but-2-ene and *trans*-but-2-ene on MoS_2 catalyst at 350° ⁹.

References

1. E. E. DONATH, *Adv. Catal.*, 1956, 8, 239.
2. O. J. WRIGHT, C. SAMPSON, D. FRASER, R. B. MOYRS and P. B. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1960, 1585.

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3. K. TANAKA, T. OKUHARA, S. SATO and K. MIYAHARA, *J. Catal.*, 1976, 43, 860.
4. T. OKUHARA, K. TANAKA and K. MIYAHARA, *J. Catal.*, 1977, 48, 229.
5. T. OKUHARA, T. KONDO, K. TANAKA and K. MIYAHARA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, 81, 90.
6. K. C. CAMPBELL, M. L. MIRZA, S. J. THOMSON and G. WEBB, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1984, 1689.
7. K. C. CAMPBELL, M. L. MIRZA, S. J. THOMSON and G. WEBB, *Analyst*, 1985, 1039.
8. J. E. KILPATRICK, E. J. PROSEN, K. S. FITZER and F. D. ROSSINI, *J. Res. Bur. Stand.*, 1946, 36, 590.
9. Unpublished results.